

SNAP-THROUGH MOTION ESTIMATION OF A BUCKLED BISTABLE COMPOSITE BEAM

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the analytical modelling of the snap-through behaviour of a clamp-clamp pre-compressed or buckled bistable composite beam. The analytical modelling considers only spatial behaviour. The beam is modelled by considering an Euler-Bernoulli beam with an initial imperfection and the small deflection theory. The modelling considers only the first two buckling modes of the beam. A simple algorithm is proposed to solve the snap-through sequence from two equations with three unknowns. The algorithm is validated by performing an experiment using a high-speed camera recording. The camera image is processed using a developed MATLAB code. The beam is actuated at the centre and off-axis, using a simple lever mechanism with a servomotor operated at 1 Hz. The behaviour of the beam during these two actuations, which is captured by the high-speed camera, are shown in this paper. The experiment results are curve fitted with the first two buckling modes and the results compared with the analytical ones. The influence of the two-actuation positions on the overall bistable composite beam snap-through behaviour is discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bistable mechanisms have two distinct stable equilibrium positions, which are separated by an unstable equilibrium position. Bistable systems use their deflection to store and release energy in order to maintain the two distinct positions. These mechanisms give robust design since they have the ability to withstand small disturbances in their stable states. No external energy is required to maintain the stable positions. These properties make them very good candidates for systems that require two working states, for example on/off, open/closed etc. Smart materials such as shape memory alloys (SMA), piezoelectric materials and electroactive polymers can be used to actuate them. A combination of this mechanism with smart actuator gives a system which can be actuated with much lower power requirements [1].

Bistable composite laminates have received a considerable attention due to their fabulous behaviour and potential for morphing and energy harvesting. The characterization of unsymmetric fiber-reinforced laminated composite plates as a bistable structure is well established and quantitatively determined after about 30 years of research. The snap-through response shows high geometrical nonlinearity. The increased demand for broadband vibration energy harvesters using bistable composite laminates, which are able to gain large-amplitude vibrations in snap-through motion, have recently attracted attention [2].

The snap-through behaviour is affected by the boundary condition, location of actuation force or moment and number of beams to be actuated. *Beharic et. al* modelled the snap-through behaviour of a plastic beam with flexible supports [6]. A novel approach by *Cazottes et.al* predicted the snap-through and mechanical stiffness of a stainless steel bistable beam [1] but the snap-through results were not validated.

In this study, an algorithm to determine the snap-through sequence is proposed and validated through a high-speed camera experiment. The composite beam consists of the cross stacking of three glass-fabrics and four adhesive films coated with nickel. The clamp-clamp beam is initially straight and then buckled using adjustable screws to obtain the bistable shape. This is another method to

achieve bistability apart from bistable asymmetric laminates [2-4]. The beam is actuated at two positions using a simple lever mechanism with a servomotor.

2 MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The modelling of the spatial snap-through is divided into two: (1) a virtual beam, which is Euler-Bernoulli beam without any compression energy and (2) actual beam deflection, which considers all the three types of energy. The snap-through is modelled considering only the first two buckling modes as shown in Figure 1. The effect of using higher buckling modes is observed to reduce the accuracy of the shape estimation [1].

Figure 1: Co-existing modes during the snapping

This modelling also considers the small deflection theory, where the total deflection is up to a maximum of 10 % of the initial beam length. For deflections more than 10 %, the large deflection theory should be considered. For a clamp-clamp single beam, the first two buckling modes are given in Equations (1) and (2). The virtual beam and total deflection are given in Equations (3) and (4), respectively.

$$y_1 = a_1 \left(1 - \cos \left(2\pi \frac{x}{L} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$y_2 = a_2 \left(1 - \frac{2x}{L} - \cos \left(N_2 \frac{x}{L} \right) + \frac{2}{N_2} \sin \left(N_2 \frac{x}{L} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

$$y_v = \sum_{j=1}^M y_p \quad (3)$$

$$y(x) = y_1(x) + y_2(x) + y_v(x) \quad (4)$$

where N_2 is 2.86π , M is the number of assumed imperfection modes present in the straight and perfect beam and the other parameters are given in Table 1. *Cazottes et.al* proposed a novel approach based on the virtual beam $y_v(x)$ idea [1]. This leaves Equation 4 with two unknowns, which are the first and second buckling mode amplitudes. In order to solve for that, the bending and compression energy of the buckled beam are taken into account, respectively as

$$U_b \approx \int_0^L \frac{EI}{2} (y''(x))^2 dx \quad (5)$$

$$U_c = \frac{AE \left[2(L - L_0) + \int_0^L y'(x)^2 dx \right]^2}{8L_0^2} \quad (6)$$

The actuation force F , is modelled by considering the actuation position x_F , thus, where the force is applied. The extrema of the bistable system's total energy is also taken into account, respectively as

$$U_F = -Fy(x_F) \quad (7)$$

$$U_{tot} = U_b + U_c + U_F \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial U_{tot}}{\partial a_{i=1,2}} = f(a_1, a_2, F) \quad (9)$$

2.1 PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The snap-through coefficients are solved using Equation (9). The equation has three unknowns (a_1 , a_2 and F) with two simultaneous equations. *Cleary* although applied an external moment, obtained a set of continuous solution by introducing a third equation, which is in the shape of the first mode deflection shape. There is also a guessed method where the value of "F" is assumed. For assumed "F" less than the actuation force of the beam gives five different solutions and the vice-versa gives three. Only one of the solutions correlates to real life application. In this proposed algorithm, it is assumed the second mode does not contribute to the two stable states; the amplitude of a_1 is therefore set to zero as shown in Figure 2. This leaves two equations with two unknowns to be solved. When a_1 is set to zero, three solutions are obtained with two of the solutions corresponding to the bistable beam in its two states and the last one meaningless. Two of the solutions are the same in value but with a change of sign. The third solution is zero (meaningless). A MATLAB code is written to iterate a_1 values between those two meaningful values and then extract their corresponding a_2 and F . For every change in a_1 , there corresponds three solutions. In order to know the true solution, each of the values (a_1 and a_2) are inserted into Equation (4). An error value, which corresponds to the difference between the previous shapes to the current one, is set.

Figure 2: Snap-through solution algorithm (Spatial form).

3 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

An experiment to validate the analytical beam equation suggested in section 2 has been performed with the setup shown in Figure 2. The composite beam is made up of the cross stacking of three glass-fabrics and four adhesive films coated with nickel. The beam parameters are presented in Table 1.

The beam is initially straight and then compressed by using adjustable screws. The buckled composite beam is moved from one equilibrium state to another by using a simple lever mechanism controlled by a Dynamel MX-28T servomotor. The control of the servomotor is achieved by integrating LABVIEW and ROBOPLUS software.

Figure 3: Buckled composite beam (left), and experiment configuration (right).

Photron FASTCAM SA3 Model 60K camera is connected to the Photron FASTCAM viewer software and used to capture the image. The servomotor at 1 Hz actuates the beam and the capturing with the high-speed camera is done simultaneously at 60fps frame rate and 640×640 resolution. The experiment is performed for two actuation cases: (I) Centred Actuation and (II) Off-axis actuation, using the same camera settings. The recorded images as shown in Figures (4) and (5) are processed using a developed MATLAB code. The image processing using the developed code is presented in section 3.1.

Parameters		Value
Initial	[mm]	99.6
Length (L_0)		
Final	[mm]	99.4
Length (L)		
Width (b)	[mm]	25
E_1	[GPa]	206.8
E_2	[GPa]	0.75
Thickness	[mm]	0.83
ν		0.23

Table 1: Composite beam parameters.

Figure 4: Off-axis actuation snapping sequence as captured on camera.

Figure 5: Center axis actuation snapping sequence as captured on camera.

3.1 IMAGE PROCESSING

In capturing the image, the edge of the beam is painted with a white color to give it a distinct pixel density compared to the surrounding. The adjustable screw for pre-compression is also covered with a black tape in order to match with the camera shade. The image captured in Figure 6(C) has lots of noise although camera shading was done before the experiment began.

Figure 6: Images as extracted from camera (A, B), and MATLAB (C) with pixel

In processing the image, the pixel coordinate is converted to a physical coordinate. This is a fraction of the beam length in millimeters to the pixel density. The figure 6(C) shows the beam, set-up platform and the clamps pixels in the experiment setup. In order to extract only the beam pixel, a pixel coordinate origin of 80 by 357 is first set. After, a rectangular boundary, which concentrates only on the beam, is further set to filter out the unwanted pixel. Thresholding is also done to set pixel intensity at a fixed value. For pixel intensities greater than the fixed intensity value, those values are set to one value, and the vice-versa to another intensity value.

Figure 7: Histogram of the captured image: (A) Results for all 640 levels of intensity (B) Close-up examination of important pixel intensities

Histogram of the image helps to determine which value of pixel intensity is best for the threshold. Figure 7 shows the histogram of the image captured by the camera. From the histogram, all the pixel intensities are in the range from 0 to 80. This range constitutes the threshold to help filter the unwanted pixel. A threshold value of 40 gives the best image which is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Camera image (left) and filtered MATLAB image (right)

4 RESULTS

The processed images in their physical coordinates are fitted to Equation (4). The fitted results helps to extract the amplitudes, a_1 and a_2 which are the only unknowns in Equation (4). These are regarded as the experimental coefficients. The analytical coefficients are also obtained from the proposed solution algorithm in section 2.1. The coefficients from the analytical and experiment are plotted using Equation 4 and the results are shown in Figure 9. The analytical formulation shows similar snapping sequence where it is able to predict the double jump for off-axis snap-through.

Figure 9: Analytical and experimental off-axis snapping sequence

The time history behavior of the beam when actuated at 20.1 % (off-axis) and 50 % (center) of its pre-compressed length are shown in Figure 10. For the off- axis actuation, the beam is observed to undergo a double-quick jump while the center actuation shows a smooth and continuous deflection with a single jump. The off-axis actuation causes the activation of the second buckling mode in the first jump before finally settling in the second stable state with the second jump.

Figure 10: Time history behavior of the beam: center axis (left) and off-axis snap-through (right)

One significant observation made in Figure 11 is that, after the beam has moved from one equilibrium state to another, the bistable composite beam actuated at off-axis, vibrates. This occurs because of the unsymmetric loading of the beam compared to the centered actuation. This characteristic makes the bistable composite beam with off-axis actuation most suitable for energy harvesting application.

These two observations made are in good agreement with that of *Cazottes et.al* where, a harsh shock in the system for shifted actuation and smoother continuous deflection for central actuation [1].

Figure 11: Dynamic behavior of the bistable composite beam

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study proposes an analytical formulation for the snap-through behaviour of a bistable composite beam. The modelling considers only the first two buckling modes of a clamp-clamp beam. Experimental validations are carried out by using a high-speed camera and the camera images are processed by a developed MATLAB code. The beam is actuated at 1 Hz with the force applied at the centre and 20.1 % along the pre-compressed length. The analytical results obtained are in good agreement with the experiment results.

The location of the force is observed to have an influence on the snap-through sequence or behaviour where the off-axis actuation shows a double-quick jump and the centre actuation shows a continuous deflection with single jump. The first quick jump from the off-axis causes the second mode to be activated before making the final jump.

The study has shown that, for buckled bistable composite beam application in energy harvesting, it is best to actuate the beam at off-axis. This causes the activation of the second buckling mode, which is a high energy or unstable state, and in turn causes the whole bistable system to vibrate after reaching the second equilibrium or stable state.

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